

TRANSLATION FEATURES OF TEXTS RELATED TO PUBLICIST STYLE

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Abstract. *The language is a complicated phenomenon that includes various functional styles, which focused to use in a specific field of speech. Moreover, the style is used in a text, refers the perception of its readers or audiences, in order to create the communicative meaning of the utterances. The publicist style is one of the most used in a language, that affirm the brevity of expressions, less literal words, lack of stylistically emotive devices and word combinations. The article is described the sub-styles of publicist style and their ways of translation from one language to another. The main purpose of the translation publicist texts is to convey the exact information to its recipients, preserving the communicative meaning of the utterances. As the publicist style refers to the simplicity of the sentence structure, the usage of the neutral and common words and word combinations, it gives less challenge for the translators or interpreters to transform the text to the translating language. The article includes the peculiarities of the publicist style and its sub-divisions, some specific features of the style in translation, and linguistic transformations during the translational process.*

Keywords: *publicist style, functional style, sub-styles, lexical transformation, grammatical transformation, newspaper articles, essays.*

The newspaper and magazines' articles are rendered in the sufficient details attract the translators to be more specific while translating the publicist articles from one language into another. The aim of translation in its turn remains as with the availability of understandings. While translating publicist articles the translational process must clarify the linguistic norms of translating language, in order to convey the possible perceptions for the readers. As a mediator in inter-communication, the translator should strive to keep balance between two linguistic aspects. There are many lexical units with a clear linguistic component, and in most cases, they play a decisive role in expressing the value and idea of a work. Deep basic knowledge is necessary for the correct understanding and translation of these lexical units. Lack of understanding and poor translation can lead to misunderstanding and errors in the conveying of communicative meaning. Overall, the background knowledge of the translators is very important while translating the work to target language sources. Here, it needs to be mentioned, that the translator or interpreter should not only be aware of one language linguistic units. It is highly demanded to be knowledgeable in both languages' units. So, in the publicist style translation, the language norms and the linguistic approaches of each language is considered as the main aspects while reflecting the communicative approach of meaning in the utterance. Thus, in this situation, the transformation methods are helpful to adapt the source language linguistic units into the target language linguistic norms. It is very important to remark the essence of the publicist style and its sub-styles in the origin and reshape in the target language, preserving the communicative and linguistic meaning. Translation is a complicated phenomenon involving linguistic, psychological, cultural, literary, economical and other factors. An important part of the general theory of translation is the theory of equivalence aimed at studying semantic relationships between source text and target text. As J.

Vinay and J. Darbelnet mentioned:” Translation can be given a third role. A thoughtful comparison of two languages allow a more effective identification of the characteristics and the behavior of each”. [2, p 8]. In translation we must try find the words or combination that are suitable for the norms of a translating language. In the process of translation translator should fulfil two tasks: to understand the correct meaning of the original text; to express the content of the original text thoroughly and in a perfect way. The translator should have the following: sufficient and rich vocabulary, grammar, to know the methods and techniques of translation, to have the knowledge in the branch which the text belongs to. Taking into the consideration the following skills, the translation process refers to some attitudes towards the source text units that are related between the translator and translation itself. This inter-relation can be followed by “The translator chooses an appropriate reference to the author’s style; the translator has only the one option to have a complete translation according to the source text; the translator refers for expressing his proper style and expression in a purpose of preserving the meaning” [1, p 196]. Considerably, it can be regarded as the learning field has been taken the publicist text translations where the translation process is being carried in a different aspect of linguistics. The featured points of publicist texts are their lexicon and grammar structures.

Lexical peculiarities of publicist texts are also highly developed as the other functional styles in a speech. Like a literary style the publicist style rendered in a various group of lexicons which determine the meaning of its own and obviously, their role in a base of lexical determination might be seen in the translation process. There are three types of lexical meaning are distinguished and are to be rendered in translation: referential, emotive and stylistic. Referential meaning has the direct reference to things or phenomena of objective reality, naming abstract notions and processes as well. Emotive meaning has the reference not directly to things or phenomena of objective reality, but to the feelings and emotions, associated with them. Stylistic meaning is based on stylistic stratification of the vocabulary and is formed by stylistic connotations. The aptness of a word to appear in various combinations is described as its lexical valency or collocability. As it was mentioned: “The lexical meaning valency of correlated words in different languages is not identical. This is only natural since every language has its syntagmatic norms and patterns of lexical valency” [3, p 35]. The principal types of lexical correspondences between two languages are as follows: complete correspondence, partial correspondence. Complete correspondence of lexical units of two languages can be found. They belong to the following lexical groups: proper names and geographical denominations, toponyms the name of organizations and companies; the months and days of the week, numerals; scientific-publicist and technical terms. Partial lexical correspondences mostly occur while translating process is being carried out. That happens, when a word in the language of the original conforms to several equivalents in the language it is translated into. The reasons of these facts are the following: a) most words in a language are poly-semantic; b) the specification of synonymous order; c) the differences of semantic content of the equivalent words in two languages; d) each language has its own typical rules of combinability. The liability of the words in publicist texts are measured by the acceptance of the audience. Though the words and lexicon should have to be more common and flexible to understand. Therefore, the translation process is involved to convey these lexicons in a same manner to the target language, preserving the semantic meaning of the context. So, it will be available for everybody to understand and get the proper information. For these reasons, the lexical transformations of words in translation occur in order to avoid any misunderstandings while the source text is being translated into the target language.

Grammatical peculiarities of publicist texts translation are concerned according to the grammatical structures and grammatical categories. Publicist texts are mainly occurred in a base of author’s speech, that the monologue which is addressed to the audiences expressed through the simple sentence structures. But even though, in some cases the information can be developed through the other components of the grammar structures. For example, prepositions, conjunctions, phrasal verbs, and reported speech are highly used to connect the words chain and sentence development. In oratorical subdivisions of publicist texts, the author usually addresses to his listeners in imperative moods of verbs where the attention of audiences is derived to. In order to convey the opinions in a shorter form, to make it understandable for everyone, the speaker basically uses the simple phrases in active and passive voices. Differently from the oratorical speech, the essays are rich in complex grammar structures. Fully used compound sentences make the essays unique. Mainly, essays include the described features of communication of acts, that the sentence sequences are developed through the past tenses of the verbs. The speech is expressed by the brevity of expressions, that intended to convey the main idea of the text. Still essays may include the expressions related in a scientific prose and preserve the scientific prose sentence structures. But in translation to the target language, obviously, the translator should transmit these expressions in an available format for everyone. The source text may render the complex sentences; however, the translation process evaluates the tasks to simplicity. So, in this situation, the translators refer to the grammatical transformations that help to them to identify the usages of target language grammar categories and sentence structures in the translation. The grammatical replacement, omissions, sense development and functionality are included in the grammatical transformations forms that evaluate the translation process in a highly specific features, in order to preserve the semantic meaning of the context and make it more available for its target language readers.

In conclusion it can be summarized that the translation of publicist texts is divided into the several ways of transformational translations, which are called the lexical and grammatical transformations peculiarities. Mainly, the translators need to classify the publicist texts, in which sub-style it is created. So, the challenge lays on the translators to bring into the exact translation of publicist texts for the further understandings of the recipients.

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